

Cutoff rigidity calculations for cosmic ray neutron sensors

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Abstract

The local baseline intensity for a cosmic ray neutron sensor (CRNS) is partly determined by the cutoff rigidity of the CRNS site, which is closely related to the geomagnetic latitude of the site. The best available method for calculating cutoff rigidity involves using a ray tracing algorithm to numerically find allowed and forbidden trajectories of primary cosmic ray particles. This allows one to precisely determine the lower, upper and effective cutoff values. From cutoff rigidity one can then calculate the expected baseline neutron intensity. In this paper we describe cutoff rigidity calculation methods employed in our online calculators (available at <https://crnslab.org>) and compare our calculated cutoff values to published values for the same sites and geomagnetic epochs. In CRNS work, cutoff rigidity calculations are used in scaling the calibration parameter N_0 to new locations, or in scaling various N_0 values to a common location for the sake of comparison. Such comparisons of N_0 are valuable in work with both stationary and mobile CRNS.

Key words: cutoff rigidity, cosmic ray, soil moisture, CRNS

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1. Introduction

Cosmic ray neutron sensors (CRNS) utilize neutron intensity as an indirect measure of the amount of water present near the land surface. This typically involves comparing the actual intensity (or counting rate) at any given point in time to a reference or “baseline” intensity which is usually referred to as N_0 . One nuance of the CRNS technique is that N_0 is location dependent. It mainly depends on the barometric pressure (or more precisely speaking, the atmospheric depth) and the cutoff rigidity, R , of the site. This document deals with the latter of these two variables.

Cutoff rigidity is essential to quantifying the “latitude effect” in cosmic ray intensity. The latitude effect is the tendency for intensity to decrease toward the geomagnetic equator. There are different ways to estimate cutoff rigidity, which results in different types of “cutoff parameters”. The ideal cutoff parameter would provide a unique relationship with cosmic ray intensity at any given atmospheric depth. For reasons discussed below cutoff parameters can fall short of this ideal to varying degrees, and there is a tradeoff between calculational speed and accuracy.

To facilitate accurate calculations of cutoff rigidity we have made available at crnslab.org two online calculators, Magnetocosmics (Desorgher, 2004) and TJI95 (Smart and Shea, 2001). The purpose of this document is to describe the features and methodologies of our online calculators and to examine the consistency of these calculations with published data. One of the calculators, Magnetocosmics, is also utilized by other tools at crnslab.org that require cutoff rigidity as an input (e.g. Desilets, 2021). The other, TJI95, has significant historical pedigree and is associated with decades of work by D.F Smart and M.A. Shea.

2. What is cutoff rigidity?

Cutoff rigidity quantifies the ability of a magnetic field to deflect a particle of specified momentum and electric charge. Magnetic rigidity is defined as the momentum-to-charge-ratio of a particle, and the cutoff rigidity is the minimum magnetic rigidity required reach a certain point within a given magnetic field. For the current application, the relevant charged particle is a primary cosmic ray (usually a proton), and the relevant magnetic field is Earth’s.

The cutoff at any particularly location on Earth depends mainly on the strength of the horizontal component of the geomagnetic field. For a simple dipole field the horizontal field strength increases with decreasing geomagnetic latitude and cutoff rigidity increases accordingly. The latitude effect arises because fewer primary cosmic rays are admitted at lower latitudes.

The need for accurate cutoff rigidities was recognized early on in cosmic ray work. The first cutoff calculations were based on the elegant theory of Störmer (1930, 1955), who showed that in a dipole field the lower cutoff for vertically incident particles is

Figure 1. Proton trajectories simulated outward from Honolulu, HI. Energies, from left to right: 30, 25, 20, 15, and 10 GeV. Note that the 10 GeV path returns to Earth, indicating a forbidden trajectory.

$$R_L = R_0 \cos^4 \lambda$$

where R_0 is the cutoff at the geomagnetic equator and λ is geomagnetic latitude (e.g. Kondo. and Kodama, 1965). Störmer's discovery, originally intended to explain the polar aurora, was quickly applied to cosmic ray studies. This was followed by several theoretical (e.g. Lemaître and Vallarta, 1933) and semi-empirical improvements (Quenby and Webber, 1959; Quenby and Wenk, 1962; Shea and Smart, 1967). But cutoff rigidities for the real geomagnetic field remained troublesome (Freon and McCracken, 1962; Shea and Smart, 1967), in large part because of the significant non-dipole components in the field. This was evidenced by the failure of cosmic ray surveys to produce a unique relationship between intensity and cutoff rigidity.

The next major advance came with the advent of digital computing in the 1960s (Shea et al., 1965). High speed computers allowed investigators to numerically trace the paths of primary particles through models of the geomagnetic field model, which were becoming increasingly complex and precise. These simulations proceed “backwards”, so to speak, by launching particles away from Earth (generally 20 km above the Earth's surface) to see which ones escape to infinity. This is vastly more efficient than launching particles toward the general vicinity of Earth to see which ones might be accepted at a given point on Earth. Following this insight (which dates back to Störmer) an escaping outward path for a particle of given charge will always correspond to an allowed incoming path for an (otherwise identical) particle of opposite charge. When such particles are traced sequentially at a fine gradation of rigidity (typically 0.01 GV), it is easy to determine R_L , as well as the uppermost rigidity, R_U , and the effective opacity of the region in between.

This semitransparent region (where it exists) is known as the penumbra, and consists of alternating bands of allowed and forbidden trajectories between R_L and R_U . In some cases $R_L = R_U$, and the penumbra is then zero by definition. However, in many cases the penumbra is non-negligible in that its width and opacity influence cosmic ray intensity. The problem of the penumbra had long been known (Vallarta, 1939) but could not be effectively dealt with until numerical ray tracing became available.

The problem of the penumbra pointed to the necessity of defining a new type of cutoff rigidity called the effective cutoff rigidity, R_C . While methods may vary, the general idea is to calculate a linear or flux weighted sum of the allowed penumbral bands and subtract that sum from the upper rigidity. The resulting R_C will lie between R_L and R_U , and is important because it provides a more consistent relationship with cosmic ray intensity.

Another insight is that cosmic rays measured at ground level are mainly due to primary cosmic rays that arrive at the atmosphere at close to vertical. This is logical, given that particles arriving at low slant angles (along with the cascades that they trigger) will encounter more atmospheric shielding on their way to Earth, and thus the oblique flux will be more strongly attenuated relative to vertical flux. To save precious processing time on computing machines that still utilized punched cards, it was considered sufficient to calculate R_C in the vertical direction only.

This way of calculating cutoff rigidity, as described in numerous works by Shea and Smart [see Smart et al. (2000) for a review] seemed to suffice for nearly 40 years. Shea and Smart effective vertical cutoffs, calculated using a sixth-degree model of the main geomagnetic field, have been a staple in cosmic ray studies. Gridded values and values for cosmic ray observatories were published every five years as new field coefficients became available. A version of this venerable Fortran code, TJI95, has been made public (Smart and Shea, 2001) and an interface has been provided at crnslab.org.

Two important improvements have been made to trajectory calculations since the heyday of Shea and Smart. One is the inclusion of models of Earth’s *external* magnetic fields, which also influence primary cosmic ray trajectories— particularly when the sun is magnetically active. Although the importance of external fields was apparently recognized as early as the 1960s (Makino and Kondo, 1965), they appear to have been regularly incorporated in cutoff calculations only since the 1990s. Specifying the the external field model used (if any) is now considered standard practice when reporting cutoff rigidity values. This capability is implemented in Magnetocosmics, a cutoff rigidity calculation tool that is part of the Geant4 toolkit. An interface to Magnetocosmics is also included at crnslab.org.

Another improvement is to account for non-vertical primaries (Bieber et al., 1997). This has led to a new type of cutoff rigidity, the apparent cutoff (R_a). Among other successes, apparent cutoffs have been shown to improve the agreement between latitude surveys of cosmic ray intensity conducted on different parts of the planet, and to give a more reasonable shape to some latitude surveys (Clem et al. 1997). In principle, apparent cutoffs can be calculated using either TJI95 or MAGNETOCOSMICS, since it easy to specify non-vertical angles as input for either code.

3. Methodology

Ray tracing algorithms

Because of its greater versatility, its automatic interpolation and extrapolation of field coefficients, and the greater ease of incorporating new field coefficients (which are generally available in Schmidt semi-normalized form) we rely mainly on the MAGNETCOSMICS for cutoff rigidity calculations. The TJI95 model is provided as an historically important predecessor but is not used in our flux scaling calculations.

Geomagnetic model - main field

In ray tracing algorithms Earth’s main magnetic field is represented with the spherical harmonics model

$$V = a \sum_{n=1}^k \sum_{m=1}^n \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^{n+1} (g_n^m \cos m\phi + h_n^m \sin m\phi) P_n^m(\cos \theta)$$

where V is the scalar potential, a is the radius of the Earth, r is radial distance, ϕ is longitude, θ is latitude, P is the associated Schmidt quasi-normalized Legendre function.. The parameters g and h are called Gauss coefficients, and n and m represent the degree and order of the coefficients and Legendre function (IAGA, 2000).

Every five years the International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA) publishes the best fit Gauss coefficients for what is known as the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF) for that year or “epoch”. The coefficients are based on a fit to data from observatories, satellites and surveys. When no further changes are anticipated in the coefficients, the reference field is known as a Definitive Geomagnetic Reference Field (DGRF). Values can be interpolated within the five year interval or, using the published secular variation, extrapolated beyond. IGRF and DGRF values are provided back to epoch 1900 and can be found at <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/IAGA/vmod/igrf.html>.

The IGRF/DGRF is intended to represent the internal field, which is caused by electric currents in the Earth’s outer core. However, external fields related to the solar wind can also influence

cosmic ray trajectories, a fact that has long been recognized (Smart et al., 1969) and will be discussed in the following section.

Both Magnetocosmics and TJI95 allow the user to supply the required field coefficients, although it is considerably easier to do so with the former. Magnetocosmics requires coefficients that relate to the Schmidt quasi-normalized Legendre function, and these are what is directly provided by the IAGA. However, TJI95 requires coefficients for the Gauss normalized Legendre function, which are used for faster computation of the field. The transformation between the two types of coefficient is not exactly intuitive (Davis, 2004), and, confusingly, both types are often referred to as Gauss coefficients, regardless of the normalization. Although McDonald and Gunst (1967) tried to sort out this nomenclature issue, there remains ample room for confusion among nonspecialists.

Geomagnetic model—external field

The magnetosphere is also influenced by external field magnetic fields—most importantly fields carried by the solar wind. This includes shockwaves and coronal mass ejections (geomagnetic storms) the effect of which have been more challenging to incorporate. These external field distortions are, by definition, not included in the IGRF model. But they do influence primary cosmic ray trajectories, and thus cutoff rigidities.

In cutoff calculations the external field is most often represented by one of the several Tsyganenko models (Tsyganenko, 2013). In our online calculator the options are Tsy89, Tsy96 and Tsy2001. While efforts to better describe the external field are ongoing, it is uncertain whether future improvements will produce a noticeable improvement in cutoffs, at least at the level of precision required for work with CRNS systems.

4. Inputs and outputs for online calculators

Magnetocosmics

Mandatory Input

- Latitude (range: -90 to 90N; default: none)
- Longitude (range: 0-360E; default: none)
- Year (range: 1900-2025; default: current year)

Optional input

- Month (range: January-December; default: July)
- Day (range 1-31; default: 1)
- Hour (range 0-24; default: 0)
- Kp index (range 0-9; default: 0)
- External field model (options: TSY89, TSY96, TSY2001 and No Field; default: TSY89)
- Apparent or vertical cutoff (select one; default: vertical)

Output

- R_L (lower vertical cutoff rigidity GV)
- R_U (upper vertical cutoff rigidity in GV)
- R_C (effective vertical cutoff rigidity in GV)

Optional Output

R_A (apparent cutoff rigidity in GV)
 R_C at Zenith=00, Azimuth=000
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=000
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=045
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=090
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=135
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=180
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=225
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=270
 R_C at Zenith=30, Azimuth=315

TGI95

Input

Latitude (range: -90 to 90N; default: none)
 Longitude (range: 0-360E; default: none)
 Year (range: 1900-1995; default: 1995)

Output

R_L (lower vertical cutoff rigidity GV)
 R_U (upper vertical cutoff rigidity in GV)
 R_C (effective vertical cutoff rigidity in GV)

5. Comparison with published values

Magnetocosmics

As a sanity check, I compare the effective vertical and apparent cutoffs from the crnslab.org implementation of Magnetocosmics with values reported by Villaresi et al. (2000) and Dorman et al. (2001) using an unnamed code. The purpose of this comparison is to check that the crnslab.org calculated values are generally consistent with other reported values. Villaresi et al.'s calculations are particularly useful because they cover a wide range of cutoffs and are given in convenient tables. Their paper gives daily vertical cutoff rigidities for each day of a neutron monitor latitude survey from 1996-97. While analyzing those results, shortcomings of vertical cutoff became apparent to the authors. Their work was therefore followed by a conference paper by Dorman et al., where the apparent cutoff values for the survey were given along with effective cutoffs, also in tabular format.

One consideration is that the apparent cutoffs in Dorman et al. were said to be preliminary—but, as stated by the authors, this was only in the sense that calculations were not yet completed for the entire latitude survey. Not surprisingly the vertical cutoffs given by Dorman et al. were largely the same as in Villaresi et al., but with a few exceptions. If there was an exception then the data for that day were excluded. I selected the first ten usable data points from the survey. These cover a particularly steep geomagnetic gradient from Rome to the Gulf of Aden, just north of the geomagnetic equator.

For the crnslab.org computations the internal field was represented by IGRF coefficients interpolated between epochs 1995 and 2000 to the year and day of each data point, which is

automatically done by the code when specific days are entered. The external field was represented using the Tsyganenko 1989 model with a quiet magnetosphere ($K_p=0$), just as it was for the Dorman et al. and Villoresi et al. calculations (as described in Dorman et al. 2000). In most cases shown here the apparent cutoff is higher than the vertical cutoff.

The vertical cutoffs (Table 1) are generally in good agreement. For apparent cutoffs we notice a discrepancy of up to 0.30 GV, with the crnslab.org R_A values tending to be higher. Judging from how well the vertical cutoffs agree, we speculate that this difference in apparent cutoffs is due to the different angular weighting schemes employed.

Table 1. Comparison of Dorman et al. (20001) reported cutoffs (D) to those from Magnetocosmics as implemented on crnslab.org (MC) along with the difference, Δ .

Day	N. Lat	E. Lon	R_c , GV			R_A , GV		
			D	MC	Δ	D	MC	Δ
21-Dec-96	44.4	12.38	5.20	5.08	-0.12	5.17	5.21	0.04
22-Dec-96	41.76	16.56	6.26	6.26	0.00	6.30	6.26	-0.04
23-Dec-96	37.25	21.27	8.61	8.66	0.05	8.76	8.75	-0.01
24-Dec-96	33.86	26.88	9.90	9.95	0.05	10.19	10.45	0.26
25-Dec-96	31.56	31.92	11.10	11.14	0.04	11.44	11.59	0.15
26-Dec-96	30.06	32.55	11.82	11.86	0.04	12.11	12.41	0.30
28-Dec-96	20.82	38.54	14.91	14.90	-0.01	15.45	15.71	0.26
29-Dec-96	16.49	41.15	15.58	15.59	0.01	16.18	16.45	0.27
30-Dec-96	12.84	44.25	15.95	15.97	0.02	16.58	16.86	0.28
31-Dec-96	12.24	49.68	16.18	16.20	0.02	16.82	17.10	0.28

TJI95

M.A. Shea and D.F. Smart have reported numerous cutoffs over a career spanning nearly 40 years. Most of those results, we presume, were calculated using TJI95 or its closely related predecessor. It is therefore worthwhile, as a sanity check, to compare the results of the crnslab.org online implementation of TJI95 with data reported by Shea and Smart themselves. For this comparison I chose the data in Shea and Smart (2001), which was published the same year as the TJI95 documentation (Smart and Shea, 2001).

Shea and Smart (2001) list cutoff rigidities for all neutron monitor observatory sites which are known to have existed. The data are given in five year intervals from 1955 to 1995. We chose a selection of 15 sites representing a broad profile of geomagnetic latitudes and longitudes and covering all seven continents.

The comparison shows very good ($\Delta \leq 0.01$ GV) to good ($\Delta \leq 0.05$ GV) agreement most of the time (Tables 2 and 3). One exception is Hermanus, South Africa in 1955 where the crnslab.org value is lower by 0.30 GV. While the difference is surprising given that the same code was used in both cases, it seems that vertical cutoff rigidities in this region have long been problematic (Stoker et al., 1997). The difference may also be due to slightly different field representations in the model. In any case, the use of apparent cutoff rigidities have proved particularly advantageous in this area according to Stoker et al. (1997).

A more significant and persistent disagreement is found over Beijing, where our value is higher by 0.43 GV for epoch 1955 and lower by a similar amount (0.45 GV) for epoch 1995. The reasons may also be related to the field representation or an anomaly in the region, or both. This might be another example of a region where apparent cutoffs are advantageous over vertical ones. Interestingly, the anomaly does not extend to Mt. Norikura, Japan, where results are in reasonable agreement for both epochs.

With the two outlier sites removed, the remaining values agree to within at least 0.1 GV, and usually to within better than 0.03 GV. While this level of agreement is acceptable, it is still puzzling that the values do not agree better, particularly for epoch 1995. One possibility is that the IGRF coefficients have been slightly revised between when the calculations were performed.

Table 2. Comparison of Shea and Smart (2001) reported cutoffs (S&S) to those from TJI95 (Smart and Shea, 2001) as implemented on crnslab.org (TJI) along with the difference Δ . All values are for epoch 1955.0.

Station	N. lat.	E. long.	R_c , GV		
			S&S	TJI	Δ
Yakutsk, Russia	62.03	129.73	1.61	1.70	0.09
Climax, USA	39.37	253.82	3.06	3.08	0.02
Halle, Germany	51.48	11.97	3.07	3.12	0.05
Larc, Antarctica	-62.20	301.04	3.77	3.80	0.03
Jungfrauoch, Switzerland	46.55	7.98	4.53	4.53	0.00
Hermanus, South Africa	-34.42	19.22	4.84	4.54	-0.30
Alma Ata-U, Kazakhstan	43.25	76.92	6.73	6.76	0.03
Brisbane, Australia	-27.42	153.12	7.40	7.32	-0.08
Erevan, Armenia	40.17	44.25	7.81	7.81	0.00
Buenos Aires, Argentina	-34.60	301.52	10.63	10.57	-0.06
Mexico City, Mexico	19.33	260.80	9.45	9.43	-0.02
Beijing, China	39.08	116.27	10.05	10.48	0.43
Mt. Norikura, Japan	36.11	137.55	11.35	11.33	-0.02
Haleakala, USA	20.72	203.73	13.24	13.24	0.00
Kodaikanal, India	10.23	77.48	17.47	17.47	0.00

Table 3. Comparison of Shea and Smart (2001) reported cutoffs (S&S) to those from TJI95 (Smart and Shea, 2001) as implemented on crnslab.org (DD) along with the difference, Δ . Calculations for epoch 1995.0.

Station	N. Lat	E. long	R_c , GV		
			S&S	TJI	Δ
Yakutsk, Russia	62.03	129.73	1.55	1.52	-0.03
Climax, USA	39.37	253.82	2.93	2.93	0.00
Halle, Germany	51.48	11.97	3.07	3.00	-0.07
Larc, Antarctica	-62.20	301.04	3.01	2.98	-0.03
Jungfrauoch, Switzerland	46.55	7.98	4.59	4.60	0.01
Hermanus, South Africa	-34.42	19.22	4.45	4.43	-0.02
Alma Ata-U, Kazakhstan	43.25	76.92	6.45	6.41	-0.04
Brisbane, Australia	-27.42	153.12	7.08	7.03	-0.05
Erevan, Armenia	40.17	44.25	7.36	7.36	0.00
Buenos Aires, Argentina	-34.60	301.52	9.09	9.07	-0.02
Mexico City, Mexico	19.33	260.80	8.02	8.01	-0.01
Beijing, China	39.08	116.27	10.22	9.77	-0.45
Mt. Norikura, Japan	36.11	137.55	11.25	11.21	-0.04
Haleakala, USA	20.72	203.73	12.76	12.77	0.01
Kodaikanal, India	10.23	77.48	17.33	17.34	0.01

Summary

Neutron intensity is in part determined by cutoff rigidity. However, there are varying definitions of cutoff rigidity, and multiple ways to calculate it. The code Magnetocosmics seems to be the state of the art, and most easily incorporates external fields. We provide a user interface for this code and also for a predecessor called TJI95. Our implementation of these codes provides values that are mostly consistent with other published cutoffs. The Magnetocosmics code provides the cutoff rigidities used in the flux calculator on crnslab.org.

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Revision History